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Review Article

Interface between anode porous transport layer and catalyst layer: A key to efficient, stable and competitive proton exchange membrane water electrolysis

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This review examines advancements in the design of the anode porous transport layer (PTL) and catalyst layer (CL) interface in proton exchange membrane water electrolysis (PEMWE). The quality of PTL-CL interface (contact area and contact resistance per area) is critical to electrolyser performance, influencing the voltage losses (polarisation and ohmic) and stability. To mitigate issues associated with Ti PTL passivation and enhance charge transport, various noble metal coatings, have been explored. Ir coatings seems to be the optimal solution due to their stability and catalytic activity. The review highlights surface modification techniques such as physical vapour deposition, electroplating, and laser ablation, as well as the development of porous transport electrodes and microporous layers. These approaches aim to optimise the performance of the electrolyser while minimising the noble metal usage. The findings underscore the importance of material choice and nano/microscale morphology of the interface in achieving cost-effective and durable PEMWE systems.

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Corresponding author: Bouzek, Karel (Karel.Bouzek@vscht.cz)**Current Opinion in Electrochemistry** 2025, 49:101624This review comes from a themed issue on **Energy transformation 2025**.Edited by **Hamish Andrew Miller** and **Liang An**.For a complete overview see the [Issue](#) and the [Editorial](#)

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coelec.2024.101624>2451-9103/© 2024 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).**Keywords**

PEM water electrolysis, Porous transport layer, Porous transport electrode, Microporous layer, Platinum group metals, Titanium.

Introduction

Proton exchange membrane water electrolysis (PEMWE) is gaining importance due to the global push for renewable energy in industry, highlighting the need for cost-effective, reliable and sustainable hydrogen generation technologies to meet future targets [1]. Compared to other technologies, PEMWE produces highly pure hydrogen at high current densities with relatively compact devices capable of operating under increased pressure. However, the primary drawback of PEMWE is the high investment cost due to the use of expensive construction materials. On the cathode side, carbon-supported Pt nanoparticles, in combination with a carbon-based porous transport layer (PTL), are used. The harsh conditions present on the anode side, caused by the high acidity of the membrane and high anode potentials, necessitate the use of corrosion-resistant materials such as Ti and Pt-group metals (PGMs). Ti is used for bipolar plates and the anode PTL, which can be either in the form of sintered material or felt. PGMs are used as catalysts in the catalyst layer (CL) deposited typically on the membrane.

The oxidative environment in the anode compartment causes the formation of a compact surface oxide on the Ti, leading to significant contact resistance between the PTL and the catalyst layer, resulting in PEMWE performance decay. To avoid this effect and ensure long-term stable operation, the PTL is generally coated with a PGM layer, which further increases the already high consumption of PGMs.

To address this issue, it is essential to develop a smartly designed PTL-CL interface. This may involve creating functional surface morphologies on the PTL through nanostructuring of the coating and/or the use of a microporous layer (MPL). Such an optimised interface enables minimising loading of PGMs while maintaining high effectiveness and efficiency. This review highlights cutting-edge research in this area, with a particular emphasis on publications from the years 2022–2024. A

tables summarising referenced papers with details about materials, experimental methods and electrolyser performances are included in the Supporting Information file.

Porous transport layer surface treatment and coating

The PTL-CL interface significantly impacts the overall electrolyser performance. Not only it is necessary to carefully design the morphology of the PTL to avoid unnecessary voltage losses connected to mass transport, but it is also important to pay attention to its charge transport properties. Figure 1 schematically summarises individual approaches used to improve PTL-CL interface properties when compared to the pristine PTL discussed later on in the text.

Coatings for excessive passivation protection

During PEMWE operation, a resistive Ti oxide forms on the anode Ti PTL surface, causing rapid performance degradation. Rakousky et al. [2] reported that after operation at 2 A cm^{-2} for 1000 h, the ohmic voltage losses arising from Ti PTL passivation accounted for 78 % of the overall voltage losses. Moreover, current flow through the poorly conductive Ti oxide generates heat, creating hot spots that cause damage to the CL and leading to its delamination [3,4]. Data from multiple reports also show less efficient utilisation of the catalyst within the CL when anode Ti PTL without any surface treatment is used, resulting in higher apparent activation voltage losses [2,5,6].

To mitigate these issues, the anode PTLs in PEMWE are coated with a thin layer of PGM (Au, Pt or Ir). Pt [2,6–9] and Au [6,9,10] coatings only protect the Ti

PTL against oxidation. Pt coatings are preferable as they provide excellent long-term stability to the anode PTL-CL interface, unlike Au which is prone to dissolution [6,9]. Ir and Ir-based [3–6,9,11–19] coatings provide not only reliable protection to the PTL but also catalytic activity for oxygen evolution reaction. Co-deposition of IrO_2 and TiO_2 , along with more sophisticated mixed oxides containing Ti, Ir and Ta were explored, although the stability of these coatings is questionable [16–18]. The harsh conditions present in the anode compartment largely limit the options for the coating material selection, and mostly only PGM-based materials were reported to fulfil the requirements for stability and conductivity. An exception is a study published by Stiber et al. [20]. They coated a stainless steel PTL with Ti and subsequently with Nb resulting in a promising and economically feasible solution. Observed degradation after 1400 h of operation (about 20% voltage increase at 2 A cm^{-2}) was ascribed to changes in the CCM.

Before applying PMG coatings, many researchers perform a chemical pre-treatment of the Ti PTL using various acids or etchants, such as oxalic acid [12,16,17] or HCl [18,19,21]. These treatments allow removing the native oxide layer present on the Ti surface, thus reducing the contact resistance between the PTL and CL and ensure better reproducibility of results [19]. Further decrease of the interfacial resistance can be achieved by employing additional pre-treatments to the surface. In our recent work, it was demonstrated that introducing a thin layer of (electro)chemically formed Ti hydride on the Ti PTL surface significantly decreases the ohmic resistance of the electrolyser cell [19,21,22]. While the surface hydride partially stabilises the PTL against oxidation [19,21], it was not sufficiently stable

Figure 1

Schematic representation of PTL-CL interface modifications. Impact on the electrolysis polarisation curve is indicated as well. Individual modification methods shown are noted in the figure.

for practical application. However, combining surface hydridation with subsequent Ir coating resulted in both very low contact resistance and reliable stability [19].

Coating formation is most commonly achieved through physical vapour deposition techniques, such as arc plasma deposition [11,15,23] or sputter coating [2–7,9,14,19] and less commonly, electroplating [8,10,12,13]. For depositing oxide coatings, thermal decomposition of precursors sprayed onto the PTL is used [16–18]. Kang *et al.* compared the quality of Au and Ir coatings made by sputter coating and electroplating [10,13]. The electroplated coatings showed better quality, featuring a micro-structured surface without cracks (corresponding PTLs allowed for better performance and stability of the PEMWE). However, it is important to note that their results on sputter-coated PTLs are not in agreement with existing literature, as many researchers report good and reliable performance for sputter-coated PTLs.

The amounts of deposited PGMs vary across studies. In reports on Pt and Au, the loadings range from 0.2 to 0.9 and 0.2 to 0.8 mg_{PGM} cm⁻², respectively. Studies dedicated to Ir coatings use loadings from 0.02 to 0.9 mg_{Ir} cm⁻². In this context, Liu *et al.* published a series of impactful papers on sputter coating of anode PTLs [4,5,9]. In experiments employing 4000 h long PEMWE operation, their findings identified Ir as the most suitable material for PTL coating due to its stability and catalytic activity [9]. Most importantly, they showed that Ir loading above 0.025 mg_{Ir} cm⁻² (corresponding to 13 nm thickness) does not further improve the electrochemical performance of the electrolyser [5]. Similarly, Srour *et al.* reported that 0.02 mg_{Ir} cm⁻² of Ir is a sufficient for a functional coating [6].

Given that the state-of-the-art Ir loading in CL ranges between 0.34 and 2 mg_{Ir} cm⁻² [17], the amount of Ir needed to effectively protect the Ti surface of the PTL can be almost negligible.

The fact that protective coating of PTL is crucial for PEMWE stability is acknowledged by the market, offering several commercial solutions in PGM-coated PTLs. For example, Bekaert, TANAKA, and TOPTI-TECH offer heavily Pt-coated Ti felts for use in PEMWE, though the information about PGM loading is, in this case, not always available.

Protective coating as a catalyst

To minimise the consumption of noble metals, some studies have reported using Ir coatings on PTLs as the catalyst, eliminating the need for the anode CL on the membrane [11–14]. This component is referred to as a porous transport electrode (PTE). These studies used between 0.085 and 0.5 mg_{Ir} cm⁻² (coatings prepared by

electroplating [12,13] and physical vapour deposition techniques [11,14]), achieving good performances (2 A cm⁻² at 1.8–1.9 V). Furthermore, the utilisation of the Ir in this design is significantly more effective, as reported by Yu *et al.* [12]. In their study, the Ir mass-specific current density in the Ir-coated PTE was 14 times higher (at 1.7 V) in comparison with the standard setup (anode CL on the membrane + PTL).

The disadvantage of PTEs appears to be a poor stability during operation [11,13]. However, this is not the case for the PTE developed by Lee *et al.* In their notable studies [7,14], they used laser ablation to pre-treat the PTL surface before PGM coating. This treatment partially melts the surface of the sintered Ti material, closes off the smallest pores, and creates a more uniform surface, effectively forming a microporous layer. First, the laser-treated sintered Ti was coated with Pt and used as a PTL in combination with a low-loading CL (0.055 mg_{Ir} cm⁻²), reaching 2 A cm⁻² at 1.9 V [7]. In the second study, the laser-treated sintered Ti was coated with Ir and used as a PTE (0.085 mg_{Ir} cm⁻²), achieving 2 A cm⁻² at 1.84 V and showing stable performance in an accelerated stress test [14].

Protective coating combined with a catalyst layer

An application of a PGM-coated PTL in combination with a low-loading CL represents an advantageous approach. In this configuration, the low in-plane conductivity of the low-loading CL on the membrane is partly compensated by the highly conductive PGM layer on the PTL, enabling good performance. In a series of interesting papers [11,15,23], Yasutake *et al.* developed a nanostructured surface for Ti felt PTL. Through a chemical treatment in NaOH followed by heat treatment, they formed TiO₂ nano-needles on the PTL surface. Obtained surface was then coated with a thin layer of Ir (0.3 mg_{Ir} cm⁻²) via arc plasma deposition. Initially, these PTLs were used as PTEs, without using a CL on the anode side [11]. These cells exhibited satisfactory performance of 2 A cm⁻² at 1.83 V; even though, the system showed insufficient stability. Interestingly, combining these nanostructured Ir-coated PTLs with a low-loading CL (0.3 mg_{Ir} cm⁻²) resulted in an impressive electrolyser performance (2 A cm⁻² at 1.63 V) [15]. Additionally, the intricate surface nanomorphology of the PTL allows for operation at very high current densities (20 A cm⁻²) without the influence of mass transport resistance [15].

The interplay between a CL with sub-optimal electronic conductivity and a PGM-coated PTL (sintered Ti) was also described by Bernt *et al.* [8]. They fabricated a CCM using TiO₂-supported IrO(OH)_x anode catalyst. Combination of its lower packing density and high activity allowed reducing Ir loading (0.3 mg_{Ir} cm⁻²). Despite its low conductivity, the resulting anode CL

reached good performance (2 A cm^{-2} @1.62 V) when contacted with a Pt-electroplated anode PTL.

Microporous layer – interlayer between PTL and CL

The main contributing factors to the cell performance loss are: 1) PTL passivation in contact with IrO_2 catalyst, 2) insufficient transport of O_2 from the CL through the PTL at high current densities and 3) non-homogeneous distribution of local current densities. The last effect is due to sparse interface between the PTL and CL caused by relatively large pore openings of the PTL (tens of microns). Additionally, this aspect may lead to local hot-spots formation and reduction of the membrane-electrode assembly lifetime due to PTL contact point passivation and the CL/membrane thermal degradation. Therefore, in the last decade, steadily increasing effort was dedicated to the fabrication of microporous layers (MPL) on the PTL, analogous to fuel cell gas-diffusion layers. Positive effects of the PTL/MPL on cell performance include following aspects:

- The electronically conductive contacts with the CL are more abundant due to smaller pore openings in the MPL. This enables higher utilisation of IrO_2 and, consequently, use of lower Ir loadings ($<0.5 \text{ mg}_{\text{Ir}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$) without a significant loss of the cell performance [24–28]. Another effect is more homogenous local current density distribution on the anode CL surface [29]. Consequently, these effects contribute to a lower high-frequency resistance of the cell and less-pronounced degradation of the anode.
- More efficient O_2 removal from smaller pores in the MPL prevents blocking of those pores and enhances transport of water to the CL [28,29]. In addition, it can be expected that this will prevent overheating of the CL-membrane interface and subsequent degradation of these components [28]. However, this only applies to MPLs with appropriate structure/properties (porosity, tortuosity, thickness, electronic conductivity). For example, high tortuosity and excessive thickness can impair O_2 transport/removal [27,28].

Two main approaches of PTL/MPL fabrication were described in the literature. In the first one, the MPL is formed by supposedly corrosion-resistant ceramic materials which should also protect the PTL against passivation by preventing direct contact between PTL and CL [30–32]. The second and more interesting method is based on fabricating the MPL from Ti particles using a vacuum sintering step [24,25,33,34]. The former approach has significant issues connected to insufficient electronic conductivity and stability of ceramic materials and does not lead to PEM water electrolyser performance enhancement. The latter approach allows preparation of advantageous, single-

phase PTL/MPL with gradient porosity. The surface of the MPL itself can be further treated to improve its corrosion resistance, e.g. by PGM coating [24,25,27]. Adding such MPL to PTL significantly enhances performance of PEM water electrolyser [24,28].

Conclusion

As shown above, advancing PTL-CL interface design is pivotal for the further development of PEMWE technology, promising significant reductions in noble metal consumption and operational costs. Coating PTLs with Ir or Pt is crucial for ensuring stable operation of PEM water electrolyser. Leveraging the catalytic activity of Ir coatings has led to advanced concepts like porous transport electrodes, significantly reducing Pt-group metal consumption. Precious metal PTL coatings also enable the use of CLs with poor in-plane conductivity due to low catalyst loadings or poorly conducting catalysts. Further performance improvements can be achieved by focusing on the PTL-CL interface morphology. Approaches such as chemical nanostructuring, laser ablation, and the use of MPLs substantially enhance the catalyst active area. However, some studies indicate that long-term stability may be a challenge for these solutions, and many papers lack data on the stability of these systems or use testing conditions not relevant to real-world applications.

Future research should focus on further reducing PGM loading without compromising cell performance and stability. This seems impossible without incorporating MPL into PTL and optimisation of its structure and properties. Moreover, the PTL/MPL-CL interface must ensure high-quality (ideally direct) contact between the catalytic sites and the PTL/MPL; thus, optimal solutions should minimise the number of interfaces the electron must pass through. This includes avoiding the use of ionomer as CL binder which leads to electronic isolation of catalyst particles. However, binder can still be present on top of CL to ensure good ionic conductivity connection to the membrane. Future solutions should also take into the account recyclability of materials, especially PGMs. All of the mentioned factors can be effectively addressed by using a well-designed PTE, where the topmost layer of PTL/MPL is coated with catalyst material, avoiding the need for a CCM. The literature shows that such solutions are functional. Further development should also address optimisation of the PTL/MPL-coating interface since suitable PTL/MPL surface treatments have already been shown to significantly improve electron transport. Another promising area for research could potentially be nano- and micro-structuring of coatings. Finally, the long-term stability of coatings and interfaces remains largely overlooked, and we stress the need for more research in this area, particularly, when considering extremely low PGM loading designs. While high initial performance is

important, the long-term stability is key to the practical application of these solutions.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT in order to improve the language and readability of certain parts of the text. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coelec.2024.101624>.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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- * of special interest
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